

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS OF THE TOPIC OF COMBATING DRUG ADDICTION

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Abstract: The article discusses the theoretical and methodological foundations of the topic of combating drug addiction, in particular the division of drug-related crimes into four groups according to their nature, as well as methods of historical coverage of this area.

Key words: "Chars", "bang", "drug addiction", "drugs", "drug".

The issue of drug addiction and international drug business has become one of the serious problems of the world community as one of the dangerous vices for society. Narcotic drugs have been known to mankind since ancient times, and their consumption had a religious character. Priests and shamans used the numbing properties of various narcotics to put the devotees into a deep sleep with various hallucinations. The spread of narcotic drugs accelerated in the 19th century, and they were used as pain relievers. By the beginning of the 20th century, drug addiction began to appear as a disease among the world population¹.

Paracelsus, one of the founders of modern medicine, said that he would not want to be a doctor without opium. With these words, he showed how important the oldest drug - opium - was in medicine in the 15th - 16th centuries. Although opium is not currently used as a medicine in its pure form, it is used in the development of alkaloids such as morphine and caffeine. Drugs developed from opium are used in the treatment of various diseases. The ability of opium to influence human intelligence has shown its power in Asia, especially in China. Opium was brought to this country from India, and in the future, plants containing this drug began to be cultivated in China itself. This plague spread so widely in China that in 1914 a total of 450 million people died. approximately 10 million of the population. a person consumed opium. Opium smoking is especially common in China, Burma and Persia, and opium is added to food in India and some other Asian countries. "Chars", "bang" are smoked. Hashish is smoked in Egypt, kif is smoked in Morocco. In South America, the leaves of the coca plant were eaten. Over the years, this habit turned into a disaster, and humanity was forced to start a fight against drug addiction².

¹ Giyohvandlik vositalari va psixotrop moddalar bilan qonunga xilof ravishda muomala qilishga qarshi kurashishning huquqiy va tashkiliy choralari to'g'risida. O'quv qo'llanma. – Toshkent, 2017. – B.2-5.

² O'zbekiston Milliy arxivi (O'z MA), M-76-fond, 1-ro'yxat, 1484-ish, 1-varaq

Today, drug addiction has penetrated all layers of society and all social groups. According to the World Health Organization, there are more than 210 million drug addicts (about 4% of the world's population) in the world. The saddest thing is that drug addiction has also spread among children. Drug addiction has affected the life of the whole society, from the simple family to the state structures. It has led to the loss of work ability and source of income, deterioration and deterioration of the situation in many families, and a sharp increase in spending on health care. As a result of the use of common drugs by drug addicts, AIDS and hepatitis increased rapidly. There is a direct correlation between drugs and the increase in crime, with drug users accounting for a quarter of serious crimes.

When studying the history of drug-related crimes, such crimes can be divided into four groups according to their nature:

- 1) crimes related to the production of narcotics: cultivation of prohibited crops;
- 2) crimes related to obtaining and distributing narcotic drugs;
- 3) crimes related to consumption of narcotic drugs or creation of conditions for consumption;
- 4) illegal actions related to narcotics, that is, illegal preparation, possession, storage and other actions without the purpose of transferring narcotics.

The terms "Drug addiction", "Drug addiction", "Drug addict" are widely used in various fields in the world, and medical workers, lawyers, historians, and sociologists are conducting many studies in this regard.

The world-accepted name of drug addiction - the word "narcomania" is translated from the Greek language "narke" - to get stuck, "mania" - strong feeling, desire, passion, and means addiction to drugs³. The term "drug addiction" means "herb", that is, consuming narcotic substances made from the juice of some plants. Also, in the legal encyclopedia, drug addiction is defined as an addiction to euphoric, sedative, pain-relieving, hypnotic, addictive or stimulating natural and synthetic substances. This concept is defined in Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances" as "drug addiction (drug addiction) - a disease associated with mental and physical dependence on drugs". Also, the concept of drug addiction is defined from a spiritual point of view as an incurable disease, which is contrary

³ Giyohvandlik vositalari va psixotrop moddalar bilan qonunga xilof ravishda muomala qilishga qarshi kurashishning huquqiy va tashkiliy choralari to'g'risida. O'quv qo'llanma. – Toshkent, 2017. – B.2-5.

to human spirituality and destroys his social and spiritual condition. In today's conditions, the terms "drug addiction", "drug addiction", "drug addict" are widely used by experts in various fields.

Narcotic drugs - drugs containing narcotic substances included in the list of narcotic drugs and controlled in accordance with the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, international treaties, including the United Nations Convention on Narcotic Drugs of 1961, and includes plants⁴.

Drug addiction is defined differently in the medical literature. In particular, in the psychiatric reference book, drug addiction is understood as a temporary or chronic intoxication caused by chronic consumption of natural or artificial toxic substances (certain drugs, food and industrial poisons). In this case, the content of the concept of drug addiction includes the consumption of any toxic substances and the resulting state of both chronic and temporary poisoning. Some narcologists noted that the term "drug addiction" should be interpreted as a general name for diseases manifested by a tendency to constantly consume drugs containing narcotic substances or narcotic drugs. Addiction is also described as a disease that can be caused by the consumption of drugs containing narcotic substances. In this way, the range of substances whose consumption can lead to addiction has expanded. According to researchers, the production and distribution of narcotic drugs gradually ensures the functioning of the narco-social state. Narco-social environment refers to all aspects of social behavior related to production, distribution, exchange and consumption of drugs. We can see such a point of view in AKireyev's scientific works. G. Dragan and B. Kalachev define drug addiction as a disease caused by the abuse of narcotic drugs or psychotropic substances. Other legal literature also defines drug addiction in this way⁵.

The terms "drug addiction" and "toxicity" are often used interchangeably. "Drug addiction (drug addiction) is a state of temporary or chronic intoxication caused by the consumption of natural or synthetic substances (drugs, food and manufactured poisons)." Due to the increase in the use of non-narcotic substances (barbituric acid substances, tranquilizers) that cause mental and physical dependence, several psychiatrists and narcologists use the term "drug addiction" to include a wider scope of addiction" and "drug addiction, they suggested replacing it with the term "drug abuse". According to some authors,

⁴ Jinoyatchilikka qarshi kurashda xalqaro hamkorlik: Ma'ruzalar kursi Mas'ul muharrir yurid. fan. doktori, professor A.X.Saidov. – T.: O'zbekiston Respublikasi IIV Akademiyasi, 2012. – B.7.

⁵ O'razaliyev M.Q. Alkogolizm, fohishalik va giyohvandlikning jinoyatchilik bilan aloqadorligi, ularning kriminologik xususiyatlari va oldini olishni takomillashtirish. Yuridik fanlar doktori ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilgan dissertatsiya. – Toshkent, 2016.– B.14-28.

addiction is a disease associated with psychophysical dependence on drugs and other similar substances. Researchers have noted several groups of substances whose consumption causes psychological and physical dependence in a person: 1) morphine and other substances that have a similar effect to morphine; 2) barbiturates and other sleeping pills; 3) substances obtained from Indian poppy (cannabis); 4) substances affecting the central nervous system⁶.

According to V.A. Jabsky, defining the meaning of the concept of narcotics should be based on the fact that, according to its legal nature, it is "drug addiction", "a person addicted to drugs", "illegal consumption of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances". , is a universal phenomenon that includes the concepts of "drug trafficking". "Narcoticism is a criminal-legal and criminological institution that includes drug addiction, as well as actions aimed at illegal dealing with drugs, which are criminalized in the relevant articles of the criminal law," he wrote. T. M. Zayko also agrees with this point of view and notes that the antisocial phenomenon related to the abuse of narcotics is part of the concept of "narcotics"⁷.

Thus, the theoretical methodology of history is one of the complex issues, the solution of which depends on the methods of source studies, historiography, historical views, philosophy and the history of philosophy, as well as other disciplines. It is especially important to comment on historical terms.

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⁶ O'razaliyev M.Q. Alkogolizm, fohishalik va giyohvandlikning jinoyatchilik bilan aloqadorligi, ularning kriminologik xususiyatlari va oldini olishni takomillashtirish. Yuridik fanlar doktori ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilgan dissertatsiya. – Toshkent, 2016.– B.14-28.

⁷ O'razaliyev M.Q. Ko'rsatilgan asar.– B.14-28.

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